

ALPMEMA: - Alpine Mountain Hay Meadow Management

D 25 Collection of tested playful approaches suited for scenario processes

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Executive Summary

The overall goal of this deliverable is to provide a collection of playful approaches that can serve as a preparatory basis and decision support for the ALPMEMA scenario process. It is based on a structured review and analysis of literature and game directories of already published and (play)tested approaches and methods within the field of scenario-planning, anticipatory governance and creative futuring.

Research shows the shortcomings of traditional scenario approaches, which focus strongly on cognitive approaches and scientific methods, while underestimating emotional aspects and imagination for future processes. Evidence from the field of anticipatory climate governance shows that playful approaches or serious games can combine cognitive and emotional dimensions and stimulate creative imagination. As serious games are too complex and time-consuming to be fully integrated into the single-day ALPMEMA participatory scenario workshop, it is possible to integrate selected playful approaches or game elements to make it a game-like experience. This is partly because participatory scenario processes share some basic similarities with games, such as being voluntary, rule-based, providing space for creativity and having a limited time frame.

A review of the scientific literature revealed a lack of research on how concrete playful approaches can be integrated into participatory scenario development. As a starting point to fill this gap, two game directories were screened to select serious games or gameful and playful approaches dealing with foresight, scenarios or at least gameful/playful learning. The screening resulted in 26 items which are presented in this deliverable and characterised in terms of: content, learning experience, rules and mechanics, roles, scale, timeframe, debriefing, digitisation, number of players, duration and licensing.

From these games and additional literature, a number of underlying game mechanics and characteristics can be derived that proved useful in game governance contexts. These mechanics/characteristics are: immersive experience, levity, complexity, game/motivational affordances, action-consequence feedback, flow experience, representation, level playing field, open-endedness, internalization of motivation, reflection/transformational learning, emotional involvement, shared understanding of facts, shared understanding of values, commitment to solution finding, social capital, sense of ownership/self-organisation, and transference of learning.

In summary, this deliverable provides a tested collection of game elements, mechanics, and motivational affordances that can be used to adapt participatory scenario approaches and make them a more gamelike experience. The mapped collection serves as input and inspiration for the next tasks and deliverables in WP 4 for the design and implementation of the Scenario workshops in the ALPMEMA project.

Goal and objectives of the deliverable and relation to other tasks

The overall goal of this deliverable is to provide a collection of playful approaches that can serve as a preparatory basis and decision support for the ALPMEMA scenario process. It is based on a structured review and analysis of already published and (play)tested approaches and methods within the field of scenario-planning, anticipatory governance and creative futuring (for methodological details on the structured analysis of literature and game directories see page 10ff). Hence, the objectives of this deliverable are to

- Provide an overview, why creative approaches in scenario- and broader futuring process are important
- Show the connections and potential added value between futuring/scenarios and ludic elements (playful/gameful approaches)
- Provide a collection of different ludic elements that might be beneficial for futuring processes, that serve as basis for the ALPMEMA scenario prototype

Consequently, the deliverable is a support-deliverable within Workpackage 4, first and foremost catering into its subsequent tasks.

Introduction and Background

Ludic elements for Scenarios und Futuring

Scenario development is a prominent approach to explore potential futures, while evoking reflective processes and promote collective action through backcasting activities (Wiek et al., 2006). It is considered a useful method to explore different possible futures and preparing for them. Particularly in the context of sustainable development, natural resources governance, food systems or community development, visioning approaches have been proven useful (see e.g., Oteros-Rozas et al., 2015). Instead of predicting and forecasting future development, participatory scenarios (and visioning) allow individuals and communities to consider different potential futures, prioritize them related to their values and preferences and develop strategies and actions to respond effectively (Hadorn et al., 2008). Anticipating different futures and preparing for different options can be considered an empowering approach, that supports individuals and communities to deal with uncertainties (Chermack, 2004). This is essential in a world where uncertainty is increasing, and communities must be prepared to respond to challenges such as climate change, biodiversity loss, natural hazards, or social disruptions. In the context of sustainability transformations, scenarios and visioning supports communities in understanding how environmental, cultural, institutional and socio-economic factors might drive their future. Sustainability transformations target fundamental structural changes that impact consumption and production practises and consequently the use of natural resources, impact on biodiversity and environmental quality and alteration of ecosystems. Scenarios and visioning allow communities to explore different futures and potential pathways towards them. In futuring contexts, scenario approaches encourage collaboration, improve decision making, unlock different knowledge systems and makes different viewpoints, problem perspectives, values and attitudes visible and thus also negotiable. This collaborative approach is expected to foster a sense of ownership, collective efficacy and develop collective action, committed to the co-created scenarios (Hadorn et al., 2008; Hamann et al., 2020; Wiek et al., 2006).

Many of the existing scenario and futuring approaches related to biodiversity, ecosystem services, climate or human wellbeing are strongly rooting in natural sciences and thus are strongly based on cognitive learning and understanding (Pereira et al., 2019). The strong focus on models, quantifiable factors and system-knowledge has fostered strongly cognitive and science-based approaches to scenarios but created a creative gap to imagine potential alternative futures and future scenarios (Pereira et al., 2019; Vervoort et al., 2010). Milkoreit (2016) stresses, that ‘unprecedented problems’ of the Anthropocene require ‘unprecedented’ approaches, that cannot be attained with conventional approaches. Also, IPBES (2019a, 2019b) in its latest assessment report refers to scenarios and models: scenarios are considered as representation of potential futures for one or more system (components), with a specific focus on the drivers of change in nature and nature’s benefits; models on the other hand are the qualitative or quantitative descriptions of system’s (systems’) key elements and the relation between these elements. Both, scenarios and models are expected to address the relationships between nature, nature’s benefits and people’s liability. IPBES is stressing the importance of different knowledge types and the importance to integrate different knowledge types (e.g., local knowledge, indigenous knowledge, scientific knowledge) and expertise into the scenario process. While acknowledging the importance of different knowledge types, values and norms in the IPBES approach, Pereira et al (2019) criticize that also the IPBES approach falls short when it comes to imaginative capacity. The strong focus on consistence, coherence and plausibility of development trajectory of entire systems, have created a void unsupportive to nurture human imagination of the future (Heugens and Van Oosterhout, 2001).

Pereira et al (2019) synthesize an overview on substantial challenges that are associated with traditional scenario methods for futuring:

(a) model-based scenarios: with a strong focus on (partial) knowledge of previous and current trends and projections, the scenarios are reductionist in several points and fail to properly account for actual complexities (Clark et al., 2016; Leach et al., 2010); their technocratic (Paprocki, 2019) and techno-fix approaches fail in envisioning desirable futures, such as multi-scale radical transformation (Moore et al., 2014).

(b) fail to hear marginalised voices and knowledge types: these scenario approaches remain in the current scenario and modelling approaches, dominated by incumbent knowledge systems (MacGregor 2009) and fail to integrate knowledge types, wisdom and expertise of ‘marginalised’ and traditionally underrepresented voices and perceptions (Bammer et al., 2020; Díaz et al., 2018). Excluding or glossing over these knowledge types can suppress the creation of impactful solutions and approaches to current and future problems. Thompson-Hall et al. (2016) stress that usually those that are most effected by environmental change and biodiversity loss are those that are not adequately involved in engagement- and decision-making processes.

c) lack of embodied feelings, hopes and emotions. Traditional scenario approaches strongly focus on predicting methods, scientific knowledge and cognitive approaches, while underestimating the role of “embodied fears, hopes, emotions and intuitions, which are necessary precursors in (re-)imagining transformative futures” (Pereira et al., 2019, p. 3; see also Burch et al., 2019; Loewenstein et al., 2001; Richter et al., 2023). Collective and individual action, reflection and evaluation are entrenched with moral and emotional precursors, that are guiding and driving our individual perceptions, assessments and motivations. Previous research from neighbouring disciplines emphasizes the importance to better consider the role and catalysing power of emotions and feelings in transdisciplinary processes (Gugerell et al., 2023), critical institutionalism (Cleaver and De Koning, 2015; Whaley, 2018) or environmental learning processes (Rickinson et al., 2009). It is expected that processes that are more emotional and stimulating empathy also have positive effects on transforming engagement into

transformative action (Heras and Tàbara, 2014). Serious gaming, playfulness or other artistic approaches are considered to cater into such embodied experiences and provide additional layers next to cognitive ones that enhance futuring and scenario processes (Candy, 2018; Pereira et al., 2019; Vervoort et al., 2022, 2010).

Parallel - and maybe partly as a reaction - to quantitative scenarios based on computer modelling and simulations various more participatory scenario development approaches have developed that tackle some of the aforementioned shortcomings and became prominent in various traditions of research on sustainable transformation or transitions. One prominent example is transdisciplinary scenario development where researchers and practitioners work together to explore future transformation pathways (Oteros-Rozas et al., 2015; Schneider and Rist, 2014; Scholz and Tietje, 2002). The focus is here on real world problems, the interdisciplinary integration of knowledge and the participation of stakeholders (Hirsch-Hadorn et al., 2008, p. 29). Those scenarios allow for the integration of different types of knowledge in order to produce multi-perspective and more socially robust images of the future (ibid.). In addition, the scenario development process itself serves important functions in that it can bring together people from different backgrounds and motivate people to take action to promote the desired future change (Chermack, 2004; Wiek et al., 2006).

Another prominent tradition is transition management (Rotmans et al., 2001) where positive visions of desired futures are created in a participatory way. These visions should provide guidelines for future actions (see e.g., Loorbach, 2010; Nevens et al., 2013) and therefore follows more a visionary mode of thinking (De Smedt et al., 2013). An example for prominent techniques that are used to create such visions is the “future wheel”, i.e. a method to identify consequences of trends, future events or possible decisions (Glenn, 2009) as used in the Manoa approach of futuring (Schultz, 2015). Another example is the more recent and increasingly prominent “seeds of the good anthropocene approach”, which combines future wheel and three horizon methods (Curry and Hodgons, 2008) to investigate how already existing innovations, practices or ideas can become part of various positive futures (see e.g., Hamann et al 2020). Other approaches that should be named are the Manoa school of scenario development, causal layered analysis or also the archetypes approach (Curry and Schultz, 2009). The following section elaborates in more detail why and how cognitive and emotional dimensions could be linked in these scenario approaches.

Enhancing scenario approaches and future thinking: linking cognitive with emotional dimensions

Future thinking and scenario development require both, cognitive and emotional processes that are touching the individual and collective level (Milkoreit 2016). Imagination requires individuals to enhance and surpass their current experience (Pereira et al 2019) and imagine a future ‘outside the box’. Transdisciplinarity research shows how unlocking different knowledge systems can enrich cognitive approaches to promote imagination. Unlocking different knowledge types and expertise require involving a broad variety of actors, including ‘non-heard’ or even agonistic voices and communities and more general – ‘non-scientific’ participants to evoke knowledge integration and co-learning processes (Bammer, 2005; Godemann, 2008; Gugereil et al., 2023; Ingram, 2018; van Mierlo and Beers, 2020). These different knowledge types provide a nuanced and multi-perspective perception on the problem and feed into the cognitive parts of the scenario narratives and actions. Co-learning during such pluralistic processes provide an improved awareness of different facets of an issue, perspectives and value-systems as well as individual and collective limits or cultural no-gos. However, as discussed above research from transformative climate governance (Frantzeskaki et al., 2022; Gupta and Van Asselt, 2019; Hölscher et al., 2022) and anticipatory governance (Burch et al., 2019; Gupta, 2011; Guston, 2014; Muiderman et al., 2023) show, that approaches focussing on

cognitive dimensions fall short when it comes to imaginative thinking, futuring and unlocking transformative action. Imagination requires more than cognitive approaches: imaginative methods to stimulate thinking about the future (e.g. storytelling, playing, creating, acting) allows a better emotional and personal response beyond the cognitive understanding of complex systems (Richter et al., 2023; Schultz and Lundholm, 2010). Stimulating these emotional dimensions let one expect that also scenarios and visions become more immersive. Supporting imaginative capacity is pivotal, since it includes surpassing known pathways and incorporate novelty into the futuring and scenarios: the prominence of defensive, nostalgic and retrotopian scenarios are an indication that imaginative capacity and power as well as novelty could not be sufficiently unlocked (Miller 2013).

Futuring: Learning from anticipatory climate governance and neighbouring disciplines

Anticipatory governance is a concept that involves actively anticipating the future to guide current decision-making processes (Vervoort and Gupta, 2018). This approach emphasizes the use of collective and individual imagination, to transcend the limitations posed by present economic, political, cultural and institutional conditions (Bai et al., 2016). To navigate such processes, there is not only a need for scenario, visioning – futuring – approaches to surpass the cognitive creation of alternative ideas, visions and pathways, but also to address the politics of transformative change (Dolejšová et al., 2021; Milkoreit, 2017). Such transformation processes require the development of individual and collective action, capabilities and the enhancement of human agency to establish and continue transformative actions to drive deep transformational change (O'Brien, 2015). Given the uncertainty of future development, it is crucial for different actors, communities and broader society to engage with this uncertainty and pluralistic perspectives. Creating environments where these alternative futures can be practised, embodied and experimented with is essential. These environments allow for the imaginative exploration and playful engagement with alternative futures, providing an environment for experiential and social learning and adaptation (Baatz, 2024; Guston, 2014; Robinson, 2003). Hence, there is a need to integrate more experiential approaches into scenario and futuring processes, that build and spur emotional and imaginative dimensions and capabilities. This can include serious games, gameful and/or playful elements (Bontoux et al., 2016; Vervoort et al., 2022) as well as the use of artistic methods (Coemans and Hannes, 2017; Dolejšová et al., 2021; Lehtikoinen and Tuittila, 2024; Mittner et al., 2023). Imagination, as noted by Moore and Milkoreit (2020) is a critical capability to build and nurture transformative agency. Thus, imagination is an important capability for governance processes, making them more robust and adaptive regarding future societal challenges under uncertain conditions.

Games, gameful and playful approaches for futuring: Roles, Worlds, Rules

The practice of using games in foresight and futuring is rapidly developing. There are several examples of games that engage with futuring or forecasting, such as online games (Dunagan, 2012), tabletop (board) games, card games, and role-playing games (Bontoux et al., 2016; Hertzog et al., 2014). Additionally, there are playful approaches, such as role-playing, theatre, staging, prototyping, or acting. These so-called foresight games explore potential futures through the medium of gaming. The time periods they cover range from the near future to distant futures and range from gameful approaches to full-fledged games. Research results provide evidence that incorporating such tools or methods can introduce plurality and diversity into futuring processes (Inayatullah, 2017). Furthermore, they create 'safe spaces' to experiment with alternative futures that might be outside the regular context, thereby stimulating empathy and collective action (Rumore et al., 2016).

(Serious) Games allow players to become familiar with different perspectives and complex system interactions in a very intuitive manner. They use situational and scenario-based approaches that create

a suitable context for creating experiences and learning (Vervoort et al., 2010). Through gaming or other playful or artistic activities individuals and groups can interact with or co-create imagined futures (Vervoort et al., 2022). Hence, games, game elements or even the co-design of games or game elements can be considered as boundary objects, enabling different people to engage with alternative futures.

Vervoort (2022) emphasizes that games are interactive systems, which are composed of three key elements: player roles, game rules (rules build a structure; create limits and incentives that structure player action) and game worlds (setting, context). 'Roles' allow players to engage with subjective experiences, to reflect on individual and collective needs, values, responsibilities, challenges or limits. Stepping into a game role allows players to immerse themselves in a subjective perspective with a future world (Crowe et al., 2007) and either identify or reject these perspectives by firstly being immersed in the role, and secondly reflecting on the role. Van Beek et al. (2022; see also Bring and Lyon, 2019) highlight the value of role-playing simulations and games for effective science-policy engagement. By taking on specific roles and interacting with others according to set rules, games can elicit various emotional responses. Rules represent systems of governance and institutions; but they can also mirror biophysical or economic processes that can blend the real world with the game world (Gugerell 2019). Both roles and rules are embedded in socio-ecological, cultural and institutional contexts. The game world describes these contexts, in which these rules and roles are embedded, by different means such as artwork, media or narration (Vervoort et al., 2010). The combination of the three elements supports interactive exploration and imaginative endeavour in foresight processes and is the core argument for blending scenario/visioning with gaming or gamefulness/playfulness (Ampatzidou et al., 2015; Ashtari and de Lange, 2019; Deterding et al., 2011). Games and foresight scenarios share characteristics, such as dealing with scenarios, decision-making, and imagining. Both allow people to explore new environments, alternative roles, and institutions (Vervoort, 2019). Serious gaming is important for understanding the educational context, as it enables experiential learning and engagement with complex concepts in an accessible manner.

Serious games are focussing on full-fledged games, that meet the full set of game characteristics: rules, quantifiable outcome (different from the beginning and valued, e.g. winning = positive, losing = negative), effort is needed to affect the outcome, active decision making either regarding other players or on the game, interacting with an imaginary conflict (Juul, 2005; Salen and Zimmerman, 2004). These more structural conceptualisations are complemented by the experimental one of involvement; Högerg et al (2019) emphasize that the systemic-experiential dichotomy is also crucial for gamification and creating playful and gameful experiences. To achieve gameful experiences three psychological characteristics must be addressed: (i) goals must be perceived as achievable and non-trivial; (ii) desire to pursue the goal, albeit under rules that are limiting the participant; (iii) belief that participation is voluntary (Landers et al., 2019). The objective for creating such gameful experiences is to spur motivation to engage in the respective activity (Högerberg et al., 2019). Hence, gameful activities and experiences do not end with the activity or the playing (the game) but extends into a post-game phase.

Serious games are powerful tools, but also require lots of time and resources to be implemented, which makes them unsuitable in many project contexts (Van Noordwijk et al., 2020). Luckily it was also shown that gameful activities do not necessarily need full-fledged games to be effective, but that single game design patterns or mechanics can also be used to evoke gameplay in non-entertainment-game contexts (Deterding et al., 2011). Furthermore artistic or arts-based research, where artistic practices and modes of expression are used to generate meaning beyond scientific understanding and challenge taken-for-granted knowledge of audience, but also of the participants involved (Barone and Eisner, 2012; Leavy, 2009). Various creative forms of expression, such as creative writing, performance, theatre, visual arts and new media, are used in arts-based research (see Leavy, 2018) and their value

is more and more acknowledged in the fields of sustainability research (Saratsi et al., 2019), because they have the potential “to embracing more than cognitive aspects of knowledge, improving communication, grappling with power dynamics, shifting relationships to nature, and facilitating futures visioning” (Heras et al., 2021, p. 1).

In summary both playful elements from serious games as well as arts-based tools could provide useful gameful activities that could be used to emotionally enrich scenario development approaches. The reason why this is promising is that existing participatory scenario approaches such as exploratory, transdisciplinary scenario development (e.g., Gausemeier et al., 1998) or also seeds of the good anthropocene (Hamann et al., 2020) show some fundamental similarities to gaming or play as understood by Huizinga (1956). Participants partake on their free will; the activities are spatially and timely limited and not linked to the immediate satisfaction of basic needs; the process follow certain rules that allow for creativity (Dannenberg and Fischer, 2017). Those characteristics can be further enhanced and expanded by adding playful elements from serious games or also arts-based approaches to turn participatory in a truly game like experience.

Figure 1: Example of a playful approach that could be used in participatory scenario development picture taken by: Cornelia Fischer

Collection of tested approaches: material and structured analysis of literature and game directories

For the preparation of the deliverable, first a structured literature review on gameful or playful elements in the context of participatory scenario development was conducted. To this end a search with relevant key words was conducted in SCOPUS. This search resulted in 130 articles that were screened for relevance. Relevant articles had to address how playful or gameful elements are integrated in participatory scenario approaches. Only nine articles were found to be of some or higher relevance. These articles were analysed to identify playful approaches and their use. During this

analysis, four additional articles were identified that were also of relevance. These articles were collected and then analysed in the same way. Playful approaches that could be identified were:

- card games,
- performances,
- online role plays,
- storytelling techniques,
- creation of artefacts,
- scientific prototyping,
- facilitation tools (e.g., future wheel) or also
- full-fledged serious games.

Overall, this literature review showed a very limited description of playful approaches and that so far there is little scientific literature available how playful elements or approaches are integrated in participatory scenario processes. To close this gap, it was decided to conduct additional reviews of grey literature. To this end, two thematically-close game directories were screened (Foresight Games, Games4Sustainability) to select serious games or gameful and playful approaches (no full games, approaches that use game elements or game mechanics), which deal with foresight, scenarios or at least gameful/playful learning. The findings can be found in the next section. Finally, in order to summarise and synthesise our findings, we also present the main mechanics and features of the identified games that have proved useful in a game-governance context.

Collection of serious games, gameful and playful approaches for futuring

The screening of the two game directories resulted in the screening of 26 items, based on characteristics derived from previously published research work from Istrate and Hamel (2023a, 2023b) as well as published research from Vervoort (Vervoort et al., 2022; Vervoort and Gupta, 2018).

Table 1: Collection and description of serious games, gameful and playful approaches for futuring

Nr.	Game Name	Short description	Source/ Reference	Learning/ Experience	World	Rules/Game Elements / Mechanics Motivational Affordances	Roles	Scale	Time frame	Debriefing Capturing	Analogue/Digital	Players	Time	License	Material collected	Game Designers	Directory ForeSight Games (FDG) Games4Sustainability
1	2 Degree Pathways	Explores how international oil companies make decisions, dynamic decision support tool to explore different pathways,	https://www.e3g.org/publications/what-happened-international-oil-companies-simulating-the-2c-transition/	learn about risks and opportunities inherent in a managed transition explore different pathways and develop strategies how to adapt to various transition pathways	narrative	Role play (roleplay company board decision making) Resource management (capital)	fictious IOCs: different portfolios	company	2017-2040	not mentioned	digital	n.a.	n.a.	unclear	no	The Oxford Smith School, E3G, and	FGD
2	2030 SDGs GAME	he 2030 SDGs Game is a multiplayer, in-person, card-based game; Learning on different projects, how to achieve SDGs and examples how to take 'real' action	https://2030sdgs.game.com/2030-sdgs-game/	Collaboration Improved understanding of real world complexities	n.a.	Cards (outlining goal of players, project cards) Round Resource management (finances) Time restriction (rounds, outlined on activity cards) Rewards (for implemented projects)	no roles	n.a.	2030	yes	Analogue/Digital	5-50 (parallel)	120-150 mins	commercial	no	Imacocollabo	FGD
3	AfroRithms from the Future	collaborative,d design-thinking based story-telling game, centres around black and indigenous perspectives, players are travellers in a multiverse, exploring possible futures and creating inventive artefacts that are sent back to other parallel worlds	https://www.afroRithmsfromthefuture.org/	Critical thinking and reflection on problem solving Anticipation of anti-racist futures Learning and experiencing democratization	2 tensions (cards) that define the world: variables that can shape the future (narrative) - these tensions will be explored	Story telling World creating Creating artefacts (by combining cards) Cards (Card Deck: Tension Cards, Object Cards, Inspiration Cards, System Cards) Voting (on tensions) Cooperation	no roles to be explored three functional roles: Seer, Librarian, Scribe Seer: guide of the journey, keep track of the time and keep conversations moving, ensures that each travellers voice is heard Librarian: researcher, if a term is unknown by the group, Librarian will look it up and inform Scribe: recorder of the journey, synthesize ideas, keep a list of artefacts created by the group,	unclear	unclear	yes	analogue	min 2	30-45 min	commercial	no	Dr. Lonny Brooks, Eli Kosminsky, Ahmed Best, Fathomers, Equitable Games Group, Jade Fabello	FGD
4	Decode the Future	create future scenarios, combination of cards create scenarios, to think about the future as playgrounds	https://futuretodayinstitute.com/wp-content/uploads/2023/02/Decode-The-Future-Game-1.zip	experience perspectives of different stakeholder figure out how to work and interact with different stakeholder practise thinking and imagining the future generate ideas and imagine alternative futures learn about different perspectives (concepts, environments) experiencing, that collaboration matters	Situation: real and speculative contexts	Cards: Stakeholder (people who could interact with or influence the future, some stakeholder are more important than others) World building/Scenario building Collaboration Time restriction: for idea generation if the scenario comes into place Counter-Reasoning: expected vs. unexpected, usual/unusual, normal / weird	Roles: Stakeholder, their perspectives and how to interact with them Different Roles on Cards	variable	5,10,20 or more years	Capture ideation one ideation sheets - explaining what's happening in the scenarios: describe the scenario (create the story, share what's happening), Explore your scenario as an organisation (What would you do if the scenario was real; opportunities/risks)	analogue	teams, 4-6 persons	no information	no information	yes	Future Today Institute	FGD

5	Dreams and Disruptions Foresight	scenario building game, that uses different time horizons; drivers of changes - and investigates different disruptions to develop robust scenarios of the future; focus on inclusion and diversity of voices in emerging dreams of the future, values, ethics, cultural and spiritual aspects	https://www.dreamsanddisruptions.com/	Collaborative visioning Collaboration Exchanging and learning from other players perspectives Exploration of potential futures learning about factors that drive change Create narratives that challenge existing norms and mental models	n.a.	Story telling Cards (scenario archetypes, time horizon, drivers of change, planetary disruptor, leaders/movements,)	no roles to explore Functional Role: Dealer (facilitator role)	global	Different time horizons, set by Cards	Open conversation centered around scenario building, drivers of change, role of leaders and movements, incorporation of stressors in scenarios	analogue	no information	no information	commercial	no	Shermon Cruz and the Center for Engaged Foresight	FGD
6	Foresight Engine	Online gamestorming engine, collecting of short tweet-length ideas and feedback	https://www.iftf.org/what-we-do/foresight-tools/collaborative-forecasting-games/	Idea collection/crowdsourcing of ideas	n.a.	Collecting Rewards: collecting points	no roles to explore	n.a.	n.a.	no	digital	indefinite	indefinite	no info	no	Institute For The Future	FGD
7	Future Disruptions Game	Tabletop/Board Game, exploring different systems: education, energy, food, healthcare, transport creating disruptive future developments,	https://future-impacts.de/future-disruptions-game	Enhancing perspectives and questioning mental models create imaginable, convincing disruptions Learn to argue for disruptions (counter-reasoning)	n.a.	Pace Competition Cards: Intervention cards Chance: dice Rewards: coins and sweets	no roles	n.a.	n.a.	no	analogue	up to 8	min 1 hour - up to half a day	CC BY SA	yes	Cornelia Daheim, Jonas Korn -	FGD
8	FutureCast	Framework for developing foresight games, developed for exploring risks and opportunities around elections, adaptable to other context	https://foresight.unglobalpulse.net/futurecast/	Discussing different perspectives learning from other perspectives creating scenarios	n.a.	Cards: Context Cards	no roles	n.a.	n.a.	yes Synthesis of the content - and transfer into actionable knowledge (what actions can we take)	analogue	10 to 20	3-6 hours preparation 2-3	CC BY unclear -	yes	Mike Masnick (Copia Institute),	FGD
9	FuturGov game	Use people's assumptions about what the future may look like to generate conversations, negotiations and collaborations through a participatory setting;	https://knowledge4policy.ec.europa.eu/foresight/topic/futurgov-game_en	Learn from conversations Render collaboration Explore new power relations Critical reflection and deliberation Critical reflection on mental models, expectations, hopes Experience collective intelligence and collaboration to create pathways to solve future complex challenges Experience and learn from different viewpoints and perspectives	n.a.	Cards Points (collecting points) Collaboration Chance: Dice Vote	Character Roles (one role through the game)		2030+	yes Strategy Assessment Governance Models: how did you position yourself towards the scenarios, does the model create a better working government, more participation, inclusion and collaboration Roles of the actors and challenges: What are the roles and challenges of citizens, businesses, government and influencers in the governance model, Learning for today: How do we need to prepare for the future? Which elements in the explored future scenarios are positive, which are negative? How to reach the positive and avoid the negative?	analogue	4-8	120 mins	CC-BY 4.0	yes	Eckhard Stoermer, Lucia Vesnic-Alujevic, Aaron Rosa	FGD
10	Hindsight 2030	Quick, light-hearted game, exploring possible futures, picking a target headline that shows a future state in 2030 - players fill the blanks up to 2030	https://blog.randylubin.com/serious-ish-games-hindsight-2030	Create pathway trajectories	n.a.	Voting: on best timeline Story telling: compelling story along the timeline, including setbacks, and reversals of fortune	no roles	n.a.	different time slot for trajectories, final state in 2030	yes	analogue	1-5	30 min	CC-BY 4.0	yes	Mike Masnick (Copia Institute), Randy	FGD

11	Imagining Health Futures	Foresight game to explore future of health in 2035, from the perspective of adolescents	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1ZWTMnG3gqjG2R2Mc95uodPoN0-GnNR5V/view?usp=sharing	World building/scenario building Learn from characters Experience perspectives from adolescents, how they deal with major crisis	na.	World building: select high impact global and health trends that are relevant to the version of 2035 Character creation: create a role/character that is adolescent in 2035 Storytelling: explore the roles/characters by storytelling: each character has in-character conversations about the pressing issue, each player talks about how their character grapples with a specific obstacle, players have some thoughts on what happens to their character when the crisis is over Artefact creation: capture experiences by creating artefacts: respond in character - written, recording or otherwise creating (a letter to the editor directly refuting the news piece, not or video to a friend explaining what happened from your perspective), audio, video journaling, piece of photography, etc. Cards	Roles (Character creation in the game)		2035	about 10 minutes: checking in with participants, creating space for feedback, ensuring that everyone submits the character information, storyline, and media artefacts Documentation: via the artefacts, media, etc.	analogue	4-6	120 mins	CC-BY 4.0	yes	Randy Lubin (Leveraged Play), Jason Morningstar (Bully Pulpit Games)	FGD
12	IMPACT: A Foresight Game	Tabletop/Board Game, critically reflect and imaginative thinking of emerging technologies in future societies, role-playing in form of different profession and pursuing their interests	https://oecd-opsi.org/toolkits/impact-a-foresight-game/	learning about future technologies Practise thinking about how this technologies evolve and influence society Assess and discuss potential secondary impacts	n.a.	Cards: Impact Cards, Disruption Cards	Roles, in form of professions that pursue certain interests	n.a.	n.a.	no	analogue	3-6	60-90 mins	commercial	no	Idea Couture	FGD
13	Money City	Players explore the future of money, makes use of a dystopian cyberpunk story, players aim to overthrow a powerful meg-cop by developing interventions on monetization, currencies, payments etc.	https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1jxSxpF8vAO54puua9hK2Oz3y6Ei_y9am	Exploring idea Develop interventions Exploring the future of money, monetization, currency	n.a.	Turn taking Resource management: currencies	Roles, in form of key factions with competing visions Singularity Now: group of investors and technologists who believe AI will solve all world's problems, Humanity United: coalition of activists, cooperatives and charities. Believes progress isn't progress if it leaves people behind. City should focus on immediately elevating the welfare of all residents The Hustle: coalition of entrepreneurs and investor who want a robust free market that will create jobs, foster innovation and make them incredibly wealthy	city	n.a.	yes Players are encourage to consider the future of the world their interventions and vision have created Ask players what they think happens next	Digital/Zoom	6-30	120 min	CC BY 3.0	yes	Mike Masnick & Leigh Beadon (Copia Institute), Randy Lubin (Leveraged Play)	FGD
14	Our Futures	Complex problems requires shifting mindsets and innovative future thinking, game pursues to provoke novel and unusual ways to unlock public imagination about alternative futures; players build scenarios, that combine different prosperities; can be played in three different modes; tabletop (board)game, cards,	https://www.nesta.org.uk/feature/our-futures/	Train innovative thinking Discussion and learning from other perspectives Critical reflection on current mental models Experiencing alternative futures Creating scenarios learning about different drivers		Cards: Technology Cards: emerging technologies, must be used in the scenario Challenge Cards: 21st century 'wicked problems' without straightforward solutions (e.g. extreme weather, droughts) Partner Cards: partners that are required for collaboration Design variable cards: changeable properties of participatory futures (e.g. shifting time frame), constraints Guiding metaphor cards: e.g. NIMBY, determines the scenario Voting	no roles	n.a.	n.a.	not mentioned	analogue	3-5 or 3-5 teams of three persons each	30-75 mins	CC BY-NC-SA	yes	John Sweeney, Jose Ramos, NESTA	FGD

15	Peek	Story-telling game to speculate about the future, based on Evan Raskob's speculative futuring, science-fiction related; structured story-telling activity	https://store.thepeekgame.com/en/	Future Thinking Creating stories Better understanding of complex relationships between present and future Learning from other perspectives by conversation	narrative	Story Telling Cards	no roles Cards	-	2020-2030	yes	analogue	2-4 (or 6-12)	45-120 min (open ended)	commercial	yes	Evan Raskob	FGD
16	Peek 2 : A game of science fiction storytelling	Science-fiction related game, to explore narratives of the future;	https://thepeekgame.com/	Future Thinking Exploring potential futures Envisioning different future scenarios Explore how the future will feel Create future story world	narrative	Story Telling World building/Scenario building Collecting Points Cards: Report cards, Feeling Cards, Entities Cards, time-period fold over cards, Tokens: cite tokens Voting	Roles/Characters (to develop)	n.a.	2040-2060	Reports on the story	analogue	2-4 (or 6-12)	45-120 min (open ended)	commercial	yes	Evan Raskob & Paris Salinas	FGD
17	Positive AI Economic Futures	gameful workshop activity, using game elements to explore positive futures involving emerging technologies, in particular AI qualitative/quantitative/target values were present,	https://blog.randylubin.com/positive-ai-economic-futures-workshop	Future Thinking Learning about emerging technologies Exploring stories about the future Experiencing individual perceptions via role creating/personae	narrative	Resource Management (Scarcity) Story telling Creating roles/personae	Roles / Personae method	n.a.	n.a.	not mentioned	analogue	4-6 per team	?	no information	no	Mike Masnick (Copia Institute), Randy Lubin	FGD
18	Present from the Future	Card-game for speculative design, based on Near Future Laboratory, stimulating creativity, empathy when creating future scenarios In [PROMPT] years from now, we will solve the [PROBLEM] , because the [PEOPLE] created a [PROJECT] , explained here in [PERSPECTIVE] .	https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/present-from-future-learning-game-speculative-design-optimism-daniel-frbzf/	Thinking 'outside the box' Experiencing empathy and feelings about possible futures Understanding the future through everyday objects Creating artefacts	narrative	Cards Roles with objectives Voting Creating artefacts Story telling Exercising problem solving Collaboration Competition	Roles in form of professions	n.a.	variable	not mentioned	analogue	2-5	120 mins	CC BY ?	yes	Daniel de Sant'anna Martins	FGD
19	Scenario Exploration System (SES)	simulation tool to explore scenarios, developed for different policy streams, like climate, fishing nets recycling, future mobility, food safety, city greening, sustainable transitions Sustainability Transitions: tool to enable participants to simulate possible pathways towards the future, role-playing, table-top (board-game-based) activity	https://knowledge4policy.ec.europa.eu/foresight/tool/scenario-exploration-system-ses_en	Exploring / experiencing different perspectives from roles Scenario building Exploring and learning of different scenarios Improved understanding of drivers Learning from different perspectives	n.a.	Cards: Scenario Cards, Real-life cards, Megatrend cards, Driver-cards, Action Cards, Chance: dice Resource management: tokens Collaboration Competition	Roles	n.a.	20 years	Discussion: participants describe and reflect the outcomes of the gameful activity, reflect on the similarities and differences between the scenario explorations Explorer Record Sheet	analogue	no information	no information	CCBY	yes	Developed by JRC Laurent Bontoux, John Sweeney,	FGD
20	SDG Boardgame	Board Game on SDGs, creative and collaborative approaches to sustainability,	https://finnstrive.com/sdg-boardgame	Learn how different SDG goals are connected Experience collaboration as necessary competence	n.a.	Collaboration Competition Cards Rewards	not mentioned	global	2030	not mentioned	analogue	no information	no information	commercial	no	Finn Strivens	FGD
21	Shocks to the System: Fast forward to 2028	Fast forward to 2028, time travelling (future) - decision making and receiving feedback on decisions around critical issues like transition minerals, food prices, climate funding decision making that will impact the trajectory to the future and instigate a transition	https://www.thefuturescentre.org/shocks-to-the-system-fast-forward-to-2028/	Learn about system shocks Train decision making - get feedback on decisions Reflect on mindsets	narrative	Cards: Trajectory, shocks, welcome cards Cooperation	not mentioned	global	2028	not mentioned	analogue	2-5	60-90 mins	CC - BY - 3.0	yes	Game Design: Alisha Bhagat and Stephanie Stavropoulos	FGD

22	The thing From the Future	storytelling and exploration of hypothetical objects from different near-, medium-, and long-term futures takes mindsets, feelings and spiritual values into account	https://situationlab.org/project/the-thing-from-the-future/	Thinking about future artefacts Explore feelings and spiritual aspects along artefacts from the future Story-telling (description of the artefacts)	n.a.	Turn taking Cards: The Thing from the Future (Arc, Terrain, Object, Mood) Artefact creation: from the four different card types Voting Arc: describe different kinds of possible futures, - Grow (climbing population, production, consumption) , collapse (system collapse), discipline (things are carefully managed and coordinated, top down or collaboratively) , transform (profound historical transition occurred, spiritual or technological) Terrain: describes contexts, places and topic areas; where the thing from the future will be found; Object: describes the basic form of the artefact from the future Mood: describes the emotions that the artefact might evoke in people from the present	no roles mentioned	global	3 time horizons: near/medium/long - term	Share photos from the prompts twitter hashtag #Future Thing Descriptions from the artefacts (template) no further debriefing mentioned	hybrid, analogue game set sharing via twitter	2-6 (4 ideal)	no information	CC-BY-NC-SA 2.0	yes	Tenkuá, Karla Paniagua & Paulina Cornejo	FGD
23	Walking the future	Exploring the future by walking through a neighbourhood and use the sights as inspiration environmental outdoor game along a planned route, each stop should have evocative stops: e.g. transportation hubs, schools, office, playgrounds, etc., develop a suitable framestory in the	https://randylubin.itch.io/walking-the-future	Explore the real-world neighbourhood Envision changes for neighbourhood Learn from discussing with other players Experience outdoors Learning from discussions, learn from other perspectives	real-world	Cards Story telling: explaining vignettes from the future Prompts: Zeitgeist (aftermath of a natural disaster, protests, economic revitalization or slump, uneasy compromises)	Play yourself in different stages of your life - personae	micro level neighbourhood	10-30 years in the future , in 5 year steps	document on social media	pervasive outdoor	4-6 players	60-90 mins	CC-BY-NC	yes	Randy Lubin (Leveraged Play)	FGD
24	Working Futures	scenario card game , exploring different economic, social, political and technological drivers, science-fiction related, speculative stories about potential futures , scenarios are short science fiction stories - basic story is prefab avoid dystopia settings -	https://workingfuture.es/	exploring trends, ideas and concepts reflecting on drivers and current mental models and worldviews learn about system driving forces learn about emerging technologies	science fiction	Cards Story telling Challenges	no roles	n.a.	20-25 years	not mentioned	analogue	1-20 players	about 30 min	commercial	yes	Mike Masnick (Copia Institute), Randy Lubin	FGD
25	The World's Future	Interactive role-playing simulation, how to deal with limited resources, develop strategies and create new ideas	https://worldsimulations.org/?_ga=2.265078982.830727438.1723451216-1325600332.1723451215	learning about the challenges of achieving global goals capacity building to tackle global challenges learn about interdependencies of global policies Explore negotiation patterns Experience, which contributions individuals can make to SDGs	n.a.	Roles: allow for specific decision making Role Playing Cards Collaboration	Unique roles	n.a.	n.a.	not mentioned	hybrid	more than 10	120 minutes +	commercial	no	Centre for Systems Solutions (CRS), International Institute	G4S
26	The Future Game	Dynamic workshop environment, collaborating in teams to make strategic decisions for a hypothetical region over 20 years	https://future-iq.com/specialised-methodology/future-game-simulation-learning/	Learning strategic decision making critical thinking develop scenarios learn about range of plausible outcomes based on decisions learn about long-term effects of present decisions train strategic future thinking	n.a.	Collaboration Competition Cards Rewards	Leadership roles	region	20 years	yes	analogue	more than 10	60-90 minutes	commercial	no	Future iQ Partners	G4S

Useful mechanics and game characteristics for activities in game-governance contexts

Table 2 summarizes the game mechanics and characteristics that proved to be useful in a game-governance context

Table 2: overview on useful game mechanics and characteristics

Mechanic or characteristic	Description	Sources
Immersive experience	Participants should feel as an intrinsic part of the game/gameful experience through different means, e.g., visualization or interactive stories.	(Burke, 2016; Checa and Bustillo, 2020; Dede, 2009)
Levity	A game is expected to draw players into playing and interacting with it, with balanced seriousness-	(Burke, 2016; Hertzog et al., 2014; Lankford and Watson, 2007)
Complexity	Game or gameful environment resembles real-world-complexities (i.e., data, models, social complexity, etc.)	(Aubert et al., 2019; Lankford and Watson, 2007; Wesselow and Stoll-Kleemann, 2018)
Game/motivational affordances	Game/motivational affordances are included (e.g., points, leader boards, achievements/badges, levels, theme, clear goals, rewards, progress, challenge)	(Aubert et al., 2018; Burke, 2016; Deterding et al., 2011; Hamari et al., 2014; Seaborn and Fels, 2015)
Action-consequence feedback	Actions/Decisions cause consequences, that determine the future (development) of the scenario and/or further action	(Aubert et al., 2018; Mender de Suarez et al., 2012; Plass et al., 2015)
Flow experience	Deep absorption that the game facilitates for participants (i.e., symbiosis between challenges and the skills needed to meet them, skills neither outmatched nor under-used)	(Kiili et al., 2021, 2014; Perttula et al., 2017; Sweetser and Wyeth, 2005)
Representation	Representation of diversity and heterogeneity of the viewpoints and interests of the participants	(Hertzog et al., 2014; Simon and Etienne, 2010)
Level playing field	The relative absence of hierarchy and power inequities among the participants	(Ubbels and Verhallen, 1999)
Open-endedness	The space for emergence where participants accept that goals cannot be pre-determined in advance	(Kang, 2019; Ubbels and Verhallen, 1999; Zhonggen, 2019)
Internalization of motivation	Extent of participants' engagement to continue the game until the challenge is met	(Rigby, 2015)
Reflection/transformational learning	Individual and/or collective reflection of participants' game experiences that is facilitated during the game	(Gugerell, 2019; Jean et al., 2018; Lim et al., 2006)
Emotional involvement	The game/play affects players' bodily responses to, emotions about, and motivation for the outcome of the game	(Argasiński and Węgrzyn, 2019; Kiili et al., 2023)
Shared understanding of facts	Game enhances the players understanding of the ecological system in which they operate	(Jean et al., 2018; McConville et al., 2023; Rodela and Speelman, 2023)

Shared understanding of values	Game enhances player's understanding of different perspectives and interests in the SES in which they operate	(Jean et al., 2018; Medema et al., 2017)
Commitment to solution finding	Game enhances intrinsic motivation of players to find a solution to real-world-issues	(Aubert et al., 2018; Hamari et al., 2014)
Social capital	Shared game experience supports forming a collective memory, create a sense of togetherness and trust and strengthen social ties	(Lankford and Watson, 2007)
Sense of ownership/self-organisation	Extent to which the game creates a sense of individual and collective ownership in players through the game experience and outcomes	(Jean et al., 2018)
Transference of learning	Game enables participants to capture the emerging complexity of game play, help make sense of the individual and isolated experiences and fill the transfer gap between the game and world outside	(Ampatzidou, 2019; Raphael et al., 2010; Wesselow and Stoll-Kleemann, 2018)

Source: (based on Aubert et al., 2019, added additional references)

Outlook

The work on the deliverable showed shortcoming of traditional scenario approaches, due to their strong focus on cognitive approaches and scientific methods, while underestimating emotional aspects and imagination for futuring processes. Previous research from anticipatory governance shows, that serious games, artistic, art-based and gameful/playful approaches can bridge this gap and provide a more holistic approach to human-centred futuring processes. This deliverable provides a collection of tested game elements, mechanics, and motivational affordances that can be used to adapt participatory scenario approaches and make them a more gamelike experience. The mapped collection serves as input and inspiration for the next tasks and deliverables in WP 4 for the design and implementation of the Scenario workshops in the ALPMEMA project.

References

- Ampatzidou, C., 2019. Reinventing the Rules: Emergent Gameplay for Civic Learning, in: de Lange, M., de Waal, M. (Eds.), *The Hackable City*. Springer Singapore, Singapore, pp. 187–203. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-13-2694-3_10
- Ampatzidou, C., Gugerell, K., Diephuis, J., Devisch, O., Constantinescu, T., Jauschneg, M., Berger, M., 2015. The Mechanics of Playful Participatory Processes, in: *Des. Soc. Media Technol. to Foster Civ. Self-Organisation*. University Hasselt, Hasselt, pp. 185–197.
- Argasiński, J.K., Węgrzyn, P., 2019. Affective patterns in serious games. *Future Generation Computer Systems* 92, 526–538. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.future.2018.06.013>
- Ashtari, D., de Lange, M., 2019. Playful civic skills: A transdisciplinary approach to analyse participatory civic games. *Cities* 89, 70–79. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cities.2019.01.022>
- Aubert, A.H., Bauer, R., Lienert, J., 2018. A review of water-related serious games to specify use in environmental Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis. *Environmental Modelling & Software* 105, 64–78. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsoft.2018.03.023>
- Aubert, A.H., Medema, W., Wals, A.E.J., 2019. Towards a Framework for Designing and Assessing Game-Based Approaches for Sustainable Water Governance. *Water* 11, 869. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w11040869>
- Baatz, A., 2024. Transforming practices through social learning: change and stability, collectivity and materiality. *Environmental Education Research* 30, 1385–1403. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13504622.2024.2329149>
- Bai, X., Van Der Leeuw, S., O'Brien, K., Berkhout, F., Biermann, F., Brondizio, E.S., Cudennec, C., Dearing, J., Duraiappah, A., Glaser, M., Revkin, A., Steffen, W., Syvitski, J., 2016. Plausible and desirable futures in the Anthropocene: A new research agenda. *Global Environmental Change* 39, 351–362. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2015.09.017>
- Bammer, G., 2005. Integration and Implementation Sciences: Building a New Specialization. *Ecology and Society* 10.
- Bammer, G., O'Rourke, M., O'Connell, D., Neuhauser, L., Migdely, G., Thompson Klein, J., Grigg, N., Gadlin, H., Elsum, I.R., Bursztyrn, M., Fulton, E., Pohl, C., Smithson, M., Vilsmaier, U., Bergmann, M., Jäger, J., Merx, F., Vienni Baptista, B., Burgmann, M., Walker, D.H., Young, J., Bradbury, H., Crawford, L., Haryanto, B., Pachanee, C., Polk, M., Richardson, G.P., 2020. Expertise in research integration and implementation for tackling complex problems: when is it needed, where can it be found and how can it be strengthened? *Palgrave Communications* 6. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-019-0380-0>
- Barone, T., Eisner, E.W., 2012. *Arts based research*. Sage.
- Bontoux, L., Bengtsson, D., Rosa, A., Sweeney, J., 2016. The JRC Scenario Exploration System - From Study to Serious Game. *Journal of Futures Studies* 20. [https://doi.org/10.6531/JFS.2016.20\(3\).R93](https://doi.org/10.6531/JFS.2016.20(3).R93)
- Bring, A., Lyon, S.W., 2019. Role-play simulations as an aid to achieve complex learning outcomes in hydrological science. *Hydrol. Earth Syst. Sci.* 23, 2369–2378. <https://doi.org/10.5194/hess-23-2369-2019>
- Burch, S., Gupta, A., Inoue, C.Y.A., Kalfagianni, A., Persson, Å., Gerlak, A.K., Ishii, A., Patterson, J., Pickering, J., Scobie, M., Van Der Heijden, J., Vervoort, J., Adler, C., Bloomfield, M., Djalante, R., Dryzek, J., Galaz, V., Gordon, C., Harmon, R., Jinnah, S., Kim, R.E., Olsson, L., Van Leeuwen, J., Ramasar, V., Wapner, P., Zondervan, R., 2019. New directions in earth system governance research. *Earth System Governance* 1, 100006. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esg.2019.100006>
- Burke, B., 2016. *Gamify: How Gamification Motivates People to Do Extraordinary Things*, 0 ed. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315230344>
- Candy, S., 2018. Gaming Futures Literacy: The Thing From The Future, in: Miller, R. (Ed.), *Transforming the Future: Anticipation in the 21st Century*. Routledge Taylor & Francis Group : UNESCO, London, Paris, pp. 233–246.

- Checa, D., Bustillo, A., 2020. A review of immersive virtual reality serious games to enhance learning and training. *Multimed Tools Appl* 79, 5501–5527. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11042-019-08348-9>
- Chermack, T., 2004. The role of system theory in scenario planning 8, 15–30.
- Clark, W.C., Van Kerkhoff, L., Lebel, L., Gallopin, G.C., 2016. Crafting usable knowledge for sustainable development. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U.S.A.* 113, 4570–4578. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1601266113>
- Cleaver, F.D., De Koning, J., 2015. Furthering critical institutionalism. *International Journal of the Commons* 9, 1. <https://doi.org/10.18352/ijc.605>
- Coemans, S., Hannes, K., 2017. Researchers under the spell of the arts: Two decades of using arts-based methods in community-based inquiry with vulnerable populations. *Educational Research Review* 22, 34–49. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.edurev.2017.08.003>
- Crowe, N., Hodkinson, P., Deicke, W., 2007. *Youth cultures: scenes, subcultures and tribes*. Routledge, New York.
- Curry, A., Hodgons, A., 2008. Seeing in Multiple Horizons: Connecting Futures to Strategy * *Journal of Futures Studies*. *Journal of Futures Studies*. 13(1), 1-20.
- Curry, A., Schultz, W., 2009. Roads Less Travelled: Different Methods, Different Futures. *Journal of Futures Studies* 13, 35–60.
- Dannenberg, S., Fischer, N., 2017. Gaming Scenarios: Making Sense of Diverging Developments * *Journal of Futures Studies*. *Journal of Futures Studies*. 22(2).
- Dede, C., 2009. Immersive Interfaces for Engagement and Learning. *Science* 323, 66–69. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1167311>
- Deterding, S., Dixon, D., Khaled, R., Nacke, L., 2011. From Game Design Elements to Gamefulness : Defining “Gamification,” in: *Envisioning Futur. Media Environ.* pp. 9–11. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2181037.2181040>
- Díaz, S., Pascual, U., Stenseke, M., Martín-López, B., Watson, R.T., Molnár, Z., Hill, R., Chan, K.M.A., Baste, I.A., Brauman, K.A., Polasky, S., Church, A., Lonsdale, M., Larigauderie, A., Leadley, P.W., Van Oudenhoven, A.P.E., Van Der Plaats, F., Schröter, M., Lavorel, S., Aumeeruddy-Thomas, Y., Bukvareva, E., Davies, K., Demissew, S., Erpul, G., Failler, P., Guerra, C.A., Hewitt, C.L., Keune, H., Lindley, S., Shirayama, Y., 2018. Assessing nature’s contributions to people. *Science* 359, 270–272. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aap8826>
- Dolejšová, M., Ampatzidou, C., Houston, L., Light, A., Botero, A., Choi, J., Wilde, D., Altarriba Altarriba Bertran, F., Davis, H., Gonzales Gonzales Gil, F., Catlow, R., 2021. Designing for Transformative Futures: Creative Practice, Social Change and Climate Emergency, in: *Creativity and Cognition*. Presented at the C&C '21: Creativity and Cognition, ACM, Virtual Event Italy, pp. 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3450741.3465242>
- Dunagan, J., 2012. Massively Multiplayer Futuring: IFTF’s Foresight Engine. *Journal of Futures Studies* 17, 141–150.
- Frantzeskaki, N., Oke, C., Barnett, G., Bekessy, S., Bush, J., Fitzsimons, J., Ignatieva, M., Kendal, D., Kingsley, J., Mumaw, L., Ossola, A., 2022. A transformative mission for prioritising nature in Australian cities. *Ambio* 51, 1433–1445. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13280-022-01725-z>
- Gausemeier, J., Fink, A., Schlake, O., 1998. Scenario Management: An Approach to Develop Future Potentials. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change* 59, 111–130. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0040-1625\(97\)00166-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0040-1625(97)00166-2)
- Glenn, J., 2009. THE FUTURES WHEEL, in: *Futures Research Methodology—V3.0*.
- Godemann, J., 2008. Knowledge integration: a key challenge for transdisciplinary cooperation. *Environmental Education Research* 14, 625–641. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13504620802469188>
- Gugerell, K., 2019. *A Spatial Governance Approach to Landscape Planning: Insights into Coordination Mechanisms and Gameful Learning (Habilitation Thesis)*. University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences Vienna, Vienna.

- Gugerell, K., Radinger-Peer, V., Penker, M., 2023. Systemic Knowledge Integration in Transdisciplinary and Sustainability Transformation Research. *Futures* 103177. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.futures.2023.103177>
- Gupta, A., 2011. An evolving science-society contract in India: The search for legitimacy in anticipatory risk governance. *Food Policy* 36, 736–741. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodpol.2011.07.011>
- Gupta, A., Van Asselt, H., 2019. Transparency in multilateral climate politics: Furthering (or distracting from) accountability? *Regulation & Governance* 13, 18–34. <https://doi.org/10.1111/rego.12159>
- Guston, D.H., 2014. Understanding ‘anticipatory governance.’ *Soc Stud Sci* 44, 218–242. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0306312713508669>
- Hadorn, G.H., Hoffmann-Riem, H., Biber-Klemm, S., Grossenbacher-Mansuy, W., Joye, D., Pohl, C., Wiesmann, U., Zemp, E. (Eds.), 2008. *Handbook of Transdisciplinary Research*. Springer Netherlands, Dordrecht. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4020-6699-3>
- Hamann, M., Biggs, R., Pereira, L., Preiser, R., Hichert, T., Blanchard, R., Warrington-Coetzee, H., King, N., Merrie, A., Nilsson, W., Odendaal, P., Poskitt, S., Sanchez Betancourt, D., Ziervogel, G., 2020. Scenarios of Good Anthropocenes in southern Africa. *Futures* 118, 102526. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.futures.2020.102526>
- Hamari, J., Koivisto, J., Sarsa, H., 2014. Does Gamification Work? -- A Literature Review of Empirical Studies on Gamification, in: 2014 47th Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences. Presented at the 2014 47th Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences (HICSS), IEEE, Waikoloa, HI, pp. 3025–3034. <https://doi.org/10.1109/HICSS.2014.377>
- Heras, M., Galafassi, D., Oteros-Rozas, E., Ravera, F., Berraquero-Díaz, L., Ruiz-Mallén, I., 2021. Realising potentials for arts-based sustainability science. *Sustain Sci* 16, 1875–1889. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-021-01002-0>
- Heras, M., Tàbara, J.D., 2014. Let’s play transformations! Performative methods for sustainability. *Sustain Sci* 9, 379–398. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-014-0245-9>
- Hertzog, T., Poussin, J.-C., Tangara, B., Kouriba, I., Jamin, J.-Y., 2014. A role playing game to address future water management issues in a large irrigated system: Experience from Mali. *Agricultural Water Management* 137, 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agwat.2014.02.003>
- Heugens, P.P.M.A.R., Van Oosterhout, J., 2001. To boldly go where no man has gone before: integrating cognitive and physical features in scenario studies. *Futures* 33, 861–872. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0016-3287\(01\)00023-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0016-3287(01)00023-4)
- Högberg, J., Hamari, J., Wästlund, E., 2019. Gameful Experience Questionnaire (GAMEFULQUEST): an instrument for measuring the perceived gamefulness of system use. *User Model User-Adap Inter* 29, 619–660. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11257-019-09223-w>
- Hölscher, K., Frantzeskaki, N., Jäger, J., Holman, I., Pedde, S., 2022. Co-producing transformative visions for Europe in 2100: A multi-scale approach to orientate transformations under climate change. *Futures* 143, 103025. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.futures.2022.103025>
- Huizinga, J., 1956. *Homo ludens. Vom Ursprung der Kultur im Spiel*. Rowohlt, Hamburg.
- Inayatullah, S., 2017. Gaming, Ways of Knowing, and Futures. *Journal of Futures Studies* 22. [https://doi.org/10.6531/JFS.2017.22\(2\).E101](https://doi.org/10.6531/JFS.2017.22(2).E101)
- Ingram, J., 2018. Agricultural transition: Niche and regime knowledge systems’ boundary dynamics. *Environmental Innovation and Societal Transitions* 26, 117–135. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eist.2017.05.001>
- IPBES, 2019a. Scenarios and Models.
- IPBES, 2019b. The global assessment report on biodiversity and ecosystem services. Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3553579>
- Istrate, A.-L., Hamel, P., 2023a. Dataset of urban nature games to aid integrating nature-based solutions in urban planning. *Data in Brief* 51, 109800. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dib.2023.109800>

- Istrate, A.-L., Hamel, P., 2023b. Urban Nature Games for integrating nature-based solutions in urban planning: A review. *Landscape and Urban Planning* 239, 104860. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landurbplan.2023.104860>
- Jean, S., Medema, W., Adamowski, J., Chew, C., Delaney, P., Wals, A., 2018. Serious games as a catalyst for boundary crossing, collaboration and knowledge co-creation in a watershed governance context. *Journal of Environmental Management* 223, 1010–1022. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2018.05.021>
- Juul, J., 2005. *Half-real: video games between real rules and fictional worlds*. MIT Press, Cambridge, Mass.
- Kang, J., 2019. Examining scientific thinking processes in open-ended serious games through gameplay data (PhD Thesis). The University of Texas at Austin, Austin.
- Kiili, K., Juho, S., Cloude, E., Dindar, M., 2023. Demystifying the Relations of Motivation and Emotions in Game-Based Learning: Insights from Co-Occurrence Network Analysis. *IJSG* 10, 93–112. <https://doi.org/10.17083/ijsg.v10i4.629>
- Kiili, K.J.M., Lindstedt, A., Koskinen, A., Halme, H., Ninaus, M., McMullen, J., 2021. Flow Experience and Situational Interest in Game-Based Learning: Cousins or Identical Twins. *IJSG* 8, 93–114. <https://doi.org/10.17083/ijsg.v8i3.462>
- Kiili, K.J.M., Perttula, A., Lindstedt, A., Arnab, S., Suominen, M., 2014. Flow Experience as a Quality Measure in Evaluating Physically Activating Collaborative Serious Games. *IJSG*. <https://doi.org/10.17083/ijsg.v1i3.23>
- Landers, R.N., Tondello, G.F., Kappen, D.L., Collmus, A.B., Mekler, E.D., Nacke, L.E., 2019. Defining gameful experience as a psychological state caused by gameplay: Replacing the term ‘Gamefulness’ with three distinct constructs. *International Journal of Human-Computer Studies* 127, 81–94. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhcs.2018.08.003>
- Lankford, B., Watson, D., 2007. Metaphor in natural resource gaming: Insights from the RIVER BASIN GAME. *Simulation & Gaming* 38, 421–442. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1046878107300671>
- Leach, M., Scoones, I., Stirling, A., 2010. *Dynamic sustainabilities: technology, environment, social justice, Pathways to sustainability series*. Earthscan, Abingdon, Oxon New York, NY.
- Leavy, P. (Ed.), 2018. *Handbook of arts-based research*. Guilford Press, New York.
- Leavy, P., 2009. *Method meets art: Arts-based research practice*. Guilford Press, New York.
- Lehikoinen, K., Tuittila, S., 2024. Arts-based approaches for futures workshops: Creating and interpreting artistic futures images. *Futures & Foresight Science* e182. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ffo2.182>
- Lim, C.P., Nonis, D., Hedberg, J., 2006. Gaming in a 3D multiuser virtual environment: engaging students in Science lessons. *Brit J Educational Tech* 37, 211–231. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8535.2006.00531.x>
- Loewenstein, G.F., Weber, E.U., Hsee, C.K., Welch, N., 2001. Risk as feelings. *Psychological Bulletin* 127, 267–286. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-2909.127.2.267>
- Loorbach, D., 2010. Transition Management for Sustainable Development: A Prescriptive, Complexity-Based Governance Framework. *Governance* 23, 161–183. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-0491.2009.01471.x>
- McConville, J.R., Billger, M., Niwagaba, C.B., Kain, J.-H., 2023. Assessing the potential to use serious gaming in planning processes for sanitation designed for resource recovery. *Environmental Science & Policy* 145, 262–274. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2023.04.002>
- Medema, W., Adamowski, J., Orr, C., Furber, A., Wals, A., Milot, N., 2017. Building a Foundation for Knowledge Co-Creation in Collaborative Water Governance: Dimensions of Stakeholder Networks Facilitated through Bridging Organizations. *Water* 9, 60. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w9010060>
- Mendler de Suarez, J., Suarez, P., Bachofen, C., 2012. *Games for a new climate: xperiencing the complexity of future risks*. Boston University, the Frederick S. Pardee Center for the Study of the Longer-Range Future, Boston, MA.

- Milkoreit, M., 2017. Imaginary politics: Climate change and making the future. *Elementa: Science of the Anthropocene* 5, 62. <https://doi.org/10.1525/elementa.249>
- Milkoreit, M., 2016. The Promise of Climate Fiction – Imagination, Storytelling and the Politics of the Future, in: Wapner, P.K., Elver, H. (Eds.), *Reimagining Climate Change*, Routledge Advances in Climate Change Research. Routledge, London New York, pp. 171–191.
- Mittner, L., Meling, L.K., Maxwell, K., 2023. Arts-based pathways for sustainable transformation towards a more equal world. *AR* 12. <https://doi.org/10.7577/ar.5159>
- Moore, M.-L., Milkoreit, M., 2020. Imagination and transformations to sustainable and just futures. *Elementa: Science of the Anthropocene* 8, 081. <https://doi.org/10.1525/elementa.2020.081>
- Moore, M.-L., Tjornbo, O., Enfors, E., Knapp, C., Hodbod, J., Baggio, J.A., Norström, A., Olsson, P., Biggs, D., 2014. Studying the complexity of change: toward an analytical framework for understanding deliberate social-ecological transformations. *E&S* 19, art54. <https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-06966-190454>
- Muiderman, K., Vervoort, J., Gupta, A., Norbert-Munns, R.P., Veeger, M., Muzammil, M., Driessen, P., 2023. Is anticipatory governance opening up or closing down future possibilities? Findings from diverse contexts in the Global South. *Global Environmental Change* 81, 102694. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2023.102694>
- Nevens, F., Frantzeskaki, N., Gorissen, L., Loorbach, D., 2013. Urban Transition Labs: co-creating transformative action for sustainable cities. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, Special Issue: Advancing sustainable urban transformation 50, 111–122. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2012.12.001>
- O'Brien, K., 2015. Political agency: The key to tackling climate change. *Science* 350, 1170–1171. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aad0267>
- Oteros-Rozas, E., Martín-López, B., Daw, T., Bohensky, E., Butler, J., Hill, R., Martin-Ortega, J., Quinlan, A., Ravera, F., Ruiz-Mallén, I., Thyresson, M., Mistry, J., Palomo, I., Peterson, G., Plieninger, T., Waylen, K., Beach, D., Bohnet, I., Hamann, M., Hanspach, J., Hubacek, K., Lavorel, S., Vilardy, S., 2015. Participatory scenario planning in place-based social-ecological research: insights and experiences from 23 case studies. *Ecology and Society* 20. <https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-07985-200432>
- Paprocki, K., 2019. All That Is Solid Melts into the Bay: Anticipatory Ruination and Climate Change Adaptation. *Antipode* 51, 295–315. <https://doi.org/10.1111/anti.12421>
- Pereira, L., Sitas, N., Ravera, F., Jimenez-Aceituno, A., Merrie, A., 2019. Building capacities for transformative change towards sustainability: Imagination in Intergovernmental Science-Policy Scenario Processes. *Elementa: Science of the Anthropocene* 7, 35. <https://doi.org/10.1525/elementa.374>
- Perttula, A., Kiili, K., Lindstedt, A., Tuomi, P., 2017. Flow experience in game based learning – a systematic literature review. *IJSG* 4. <https://doi.org/10.17083/ijsg.v4i1.151>
- Plass, J.L., Homer, B.D., Kinzer, C.K., 2015. Foundations of Game-Based Learning. *Educational Psychologist* 50, 258–283. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00461520.2015.1122533>
- Raphael, C., Bachen, C., Lynn, K.-M., Baldwin-Philippi, J., McKee, K.A., 2010. Games for Civic Learning: A Conceptual Framework and Agenda for Research and Design. *Games Cult.* 5, 199–235. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1555412009354728>
- Richter, I., Gabe-Thomas, E., Queirós, A.M., Sheppard, S.R.J., Pahl, S., 2023. Advancing the potential impact of future scenarios by integrating psychological principles. *Environmental Science & Policy* 140, 68–79. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2022.11.015>
- Rickinson, M., Lundholm, C., Hopwood, N., 2009. *Environmental learning: insights from research into the student experience*. Springer, New York, N.Y.
- Rigby, C.S., 2015. Gamification and Motivation, in: Walz, S.P., Deterding, S. (Eds.), *The Gameful World*. The MIT Press, pp. 113–138. <https://doi.org/10.7551/mitpress/9788.003.0008>
- Robinson, J., 2003. Future subjunctive: backcasting as social learning. *Futures* 35, 839–856. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0016-3287\(03\)00039-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0016-3287(03)00039-9)

- Rodela, R., Speelman, E.N., 2023. Serious games in natural resource management: steps toward assessment of their contextualized impacts. *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability* 65, 101375. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosust.2023.101375>
- Rotmans, J., Kemp, R., van Asselt, M., 2001. More evolution than revolution: transition management in public policy. *Foresight* 3, 15–31. <https://doi.org/10.1108/14636680110803003>
- Rumore, D., Schenk, T., Susskind, L., 2016. Role-play simulations for climate change adaptation education and engagement. *Nature Clim Change* 6, 745–750. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nclimate3084>
- Salen, K., Zimmerman, E., 2004. *Rules of Play. Game Design Fundamentals*. MIT Press, Cambridge, Massachusetts, London, England.
- Saratsi, E., Acott, T., Allinson, E., Edwards, D., Freemantle, C., Fish, R., 2019. Valuing arts and arts research.
- Schneider, F., Rist, S., 2014. Envisioning sustainable water futures in a transdisciplinary learning process: combining normative, explorative, and participatory scenario approaches. *Sustain Sci* 9, 463–481. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-013-0232-6>
- Scholz, R.W., Tietje, O., 2002. *Embedded case study methods: Integrating quantitative and qualitative knowledge*. Sage.
- Schultz, L., Lundholm, C., 2010. Learning for resilience? Exploring learning opportunities in biosphere reserves. *Environmental Education Research* 16, 645–663. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13504622.2010.505442>
- Schultz, W., 2015. *Manoa: The future is not binary*. APF Compass.
- Seaborn, K., Fels, D.I., 2015. Gamification in theory and action: A survey. *International Journal of Human-Computer Studies* 74, 14–31. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhcs.2014.09.006>
- Simon, C., Etienne, M., 2010. A companion modelling approach applied to forest management planning. *Environmental Modelling & Software* 25, 1371–1384. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsoft.2009.09.004>
- Sweetser, P., Wyeth, P., 2005. GameFlow: a model for evaluating player enjoyment in games. *Comput. Entertain.* 3, 3–3. <https://doi.org/10.1145/1077246.1077253>
- Thompson-Hall, M., Carr, E.R., Pascual, U., 2016. Enhancing and expanding intersectional research for climate change adaptation in agrarian settings. *Ambio* 45, 373–382. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13280-016-0827-0>
- Ubbels, A.A., Verhallen, A.J.M., 1999. Suitability of decision support tools for collaborative planning processes in water resources management, RIZA rapport. RIZA, Lelystad.
- Van Beek, L., Milkoreit, M., Prokopy, L., Reed, J.B., Vervoort, J., Wardekker, A., Weiner, R., 2022. The effects of serious gaming on risk perceptions of climate tipping points. *Climatic Change* 170, 31. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-022-03318-x>
- van Mierlo, B., Beers, P.J., 2020. Understanding and governing learning in sustainability transitions: A review. *Environmental Innovation and Societal Transitions* 34, 255–269. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eist.2018.08.002>
- Van Noordwijk, M., Speelman, E., Hofstede, G.J., Farida, A., Abdurrahim, A.Y., Miccolis, A., Hakim, A.L., Wamucii, C.N., Lagneaux, E., Andreotti, F., Kimbowa, G., Assogba, G.G.C., Best, L., Tanika, L., Githinji, M., Rosero, P., Sari, R.R., Satnarain, U., Adiwibowo, S., Ligtenberg, A., Muthuri, C., Peña-Claros, M., Purwanto, E., Van Oel, P., Rozendaal, D., Suprayogo, D., Teuling, A.J., 2020. Sustainable Agroforestry Landscape Management: Changing the Game. *Land* 9, 243. <https://doi.org/10.3390/land9080243>
- Vervoort, J., Gupta, A., 2018. Anticipating climate futures in a 1.5 °C era: the link between foresight and governance. *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability* 31, 104–111. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosust.2018.01.004>
- Vervoort, J., Mangnus, A., McGreevy, S., Ota, K., Thompson, K., Rupprecht, C., Tamura, N., Moosdorff, C., Spiegelberg, M., Kobayashi, M., 2022. Unlocking the potential of gaming for anticipatory governance. *Earth System Governance* 11, 100130. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esg.2021.100130>

- Vervoort, J.M., 2019. New frontiers in futures games: leveraging game sector developments. *Futures* 105, 174–186. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.futures.2018.10.005>
- Vervoort, J.M., Kok, K., Van Lammeren, R., Veldkamp, T., 2010. Stepping into futures: Exploring the potential of interactive media for participatory scenarios on social-ecological systems. *Futures* 42, 604–616. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.futures.2010.04.031>
- Wesselow, M., Stoll-Kleemann, S., 2018. Role-playing games in natural resource management and research: Lessons learned from theory and practice. *Geographical Journal* 184, 298–309. <https://doi.org/10.1111/geoj.12248>
- Whaley, L., 2018. The Critical Institutional Analysis and Development (CIAD) Framework. *International Journal of the Commons* 12, xx–xx. <https://doi.org/10.18352/ijc.848>
- Wiek, A., Binder, C., Scholz, R.W., 2006. Functions of scenarios in transition processes. *Futures* 38, 740–766. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.futures.2005.12.003>
- Zhonggen, Y., 2019. A Meta-Analysis of Use of Serious Games in Education over a Decade. *International Journal of Computer Games Technology* 2019, 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2019/4797032>